

Review Article

Material Development in Language Class: The Heart of Pedagogy Approaches

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Abstract

This paper takes the position that language learning materials should ideally be driven by learning and teaching principles rather than developed ad hoc or in imitation of bestselling course books. It briefly reviews the literature which contributes positively towards the principled development of ELT materials and comments on its implications for materials writing. It then presents methods materials adaptation. It outlines and justifies each principle and then drives from it materials development principles procedures which teachers and materials writers could apply to the actual development of materials.

Keywords: Material Development, Language Class, Pedagogy and Approaches

Received: 24 March 2018

Accepted: 04 May 2018

Introduction

Anything used as a means to impart knowledge should be categorized as material (Siddiqui, 2012). According to him, materials can be in physical form in the shape of books, newspapers, handouts, photocopied papers, floppy disks, compact disk, flash drives, memory cards, audio-visual aids (e.g. DVDs), audio aids (e.g. CDs), pictures and cards, etc. Materials can also be in the form of lectures where the teacher delivers lectures and students listen, taking down points for later study. Who sees materials as instructional instruments that work as catalysts in the learning process; while Tomlinson (2011) defines materials development as anything which is done by writers,

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ISSN: 2141 - 4122

Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

teachers or learners to provide sources of language input in ways which maximize the likelihood of intake.

Pardo and Téllez (2009) argue that materials development includes the adaptation, creation of learning and teaching exercises, tasks, activities, lessons, units, or modules composed of several units. According to Thomas (2015) material development is a process guided by rules and responsibilities, but the criteria and parameters are self-constructed. This allows the teacher to promote his values and beliefs in whichever creative or pragmatic way he wishes. In doing so, materials developers, including teachers, may bring pictures or advertisements in the classroom, compose a textbook, design a student worksheet, read a poem or an article aloud. For many decades, materials development was merely the production accompanying a wide range of learning resources to illustrate methods. However, things have started to change due to teachers' awareness of two issues: first, the huge production in the interest of methodologies and materials used for teaching; and second, the importance of including students' voices in order to update teaching materials in terms of the way learners would like to learn and what they need to learn in today's increasingly globalized world. Developing materials to enhance teachers pedagogical practices involve reflection and practice because, as Pardo and Téllez, (2009) stated, 'knowing is not enough. We must apply. Willing is not enough. We must do.' This means that reflection and action go together, hand in hand, from the onset of materials development.

Adapting Materials

Materials exist in order to support learning/teaching, so they should be designed to suit the people and the processes involved. Most teachers are not creators of teaching materials but providers of good materials (Pardo and Téllez, 2009). For that purpose, teachers may conduct materials adaptation in order that they can provide good materials for their students. Materials adaptation involves changing existing materials so that they become more suitable for specific learners, teachers or situations. Tomlinson and Masuhara (2004) suggest that the most effective way of conducting material adaptation is to:

1. have a large bank of categorized materials that you can readily retrieve for adaptation;
2. have colleagues with whom you can share resources and who are willing to go through the adaptation process together;
3. have colleagues who are happy to give you feedback on your adapted materials;
4. be in an environment in which materials evaluation, adaptation & development are encouraged & teacher's time and efforts are acknowledged;

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ISSN: 2141 - 4122 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

5. revisit adapted materials and improve them.

Materials Development Demands

Since students learn at different speeds, teachers should consider this diversity when teaching the target language and when developing their materials trying, at the same time, to keep a balance among students' language learning needs, preferences, motivations and expectations, their affective needs, and the institutional policies. Language learning materials constitute a key factor in creating effective teaching and equal opportunity learning environments. Following Tomlinson (1998), these materials could be considered effective if they facilitate the learning of a language by increasing learners' knowledge, experience and understanding of it and, simultaneously, helping learners learn what they want and need to learn.

In addition, the effectiveness of materials used for language teaching depends largely on how meaningful, relevant and motivating they are to the learners. These three conditions are met when there is a match between the materials and tasks proposed in them, with the learners' needs, interests, attitudes and expectations. In other words, teachers should do their best to develop the most effective, appropriate, and flexible materials for their students and their programs.

Above all, materials development requires designers to be reflective, resourceful and receptive (RRR) agents with regard to their teaching practice, besides becoming more willing to take risks and make decisions related to the way they handle classes, and being less willing to single out what should not have been done as well as attentive to complimenting and praising their students' attempts to perform tasks in a different manner as there are not necessarily incorrect ways to do things, but rather different ways to do them.

Methods of Material Adaptation

Materials adaptation means matching materials with the learner's needs, the teacher's demands and administration's purpose. There are several methods of material adaptation. We shall consider but the following:

Addition: Addition is an adaptation procedure which involves supplementation of extra linguistic items and activities to make up for the inadequacy/ insufficiency of materials. Addition of extra materials is necessary/applicable/appropriate when the following situations are faced:

1. areas are not covered sufficiently;
2. texts/pictures/tasks are not provided;

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3. texts/pictures/tasks are fewer than needed;
4. tasks are limited in scope;
5. tasks are of limited range.

Deletion/omission: Deletion is an adaptation procedure which involves removal of some of the linguistic items and activities which are found to be extra and unnecessary. So, deletion is a process in which materials are taken out rather than added. Materials should be reduced through omission when the following situations are faced:

1. learners are clear about a language point;
2. learners are competent in a skill;
3. there are too many tasks on a particular area/ point;
4. the item/area concerned is not a priority;
5. the item/task is not well designed;
6. the item/task is not well-suited to its aim(s);
7. the topic is not appropriate for learners.

Modification/changing: Modification means changes in different aspects of materials, such as linguistic level, exercises, assessment system and so on. Modification of materials is applicable/ appropriate in the following situations:

1. Texts are of inappropriate length.
2. Materials are inappropriate to the aim.
3. Materials are inappropriate to the learners' age/ experience.
4. Materials are unclear, confusing or misleading.
5. Tasks are badly designed.

Simplification: This procedure is employed to make materials less complicated or easier to understand. If the language teaching material is found to be difficult or mechanical for the target learner, it (material) can be made suitable for the learner through the process of simplification.

Rearrangement/re-ordering: Rearrangement is a procedure of materials adaptation through which different parts of a course book are arranged in a different order or sequence. Rearrangement of materials helps to make them comparatively more interesting and appropriate for the learner as well as the teacher. Learners may reorder materials by:

1. matching their aims;
2. using a practice task for lead-in and elicitation;
3. revising an area earlier than the course book does;
4. comparing and contrasting different areas;

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5. providing thematic unity;
6. providing an appropriate follow-up (Shameem, 2009).

Essential Components in the Process of Creating and Adapting Learning Materials

The following are key components that lead us along the captivating path to materials development (Fig 1).

(Adapted from Patel, 2011)

Figure 1. Key components leading to the captivating path to materials development

Graves (1997) provides us with a particularly interesting framework for course development that is not one of equal and sequential parts, but rather one in which each individual's context determines the processes that need more time and attention. According to her, a framework of components is useful because it constitutes an "organized way of conceiving a complex process", explains areas of interest for teachers or "domains of inquiry", raises issues for teachers to explore and discover, and provides an array of "terms currently used in course development" (Patel, 2011, p. 12).

Needs Assessment

A central ingredient for developing materials is the use of systematized needs assessment procedures because it involves a set of aspects that determines teacher-decision making that will most probably help both students and teachers achieve meaningful and effective teaching and learning settings. Núñez and Téllez (2008) state that as teachers most frequently make decisions regarding aims, strategies, and

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materials that will influence their classes, those ought to be based on a systematic well-informed needs assessment. Needs assessment should occupy a prime place in materials development. In this thread of thought, Pineda (2001 in Patel, 2011) asserts that it ought to be the point of departure in making academic decisions such as syllabi development, instructional strategies and materials selection, as well as assessment and evaluation implementation. Therefore, identifying, addressing, and meeting students' needs will most probably narrow the gap between learners' needs and teaching materials that address such needs and, so, foster both their level of involvement in classroom and their language performance. So what does needs assessment entail? According to Graves (1997), it is an ongoing or evolving process that looks into "what the learners know, and can do, and what they need to learn or do..." (p. 12). Furthermore, it is influenced by a series of aspects such as the teachers' views of what the course is about; the situational constraints; the students' perceptions of what is being asked or expected of them; and teachers' views or perceptions of their students' needs as a result of prior contact with their students.

As we can see, carrying out a needs assessment goes beyond recognizing what students' lack. It implies making informed academic decisions that will, in turn, enable teachers to envision alternative learning routes to meet different needs, teaching environments, and students' profiles. In other words, implementing the needs assessment process will allow for more meaningful, dynamic, challenging, enjoyable, and effective learning settings.

Setting Goals and Objectives

Another significant aspect that must be dealt with when developing materials is the setting of learning goals and objectives. The horizon to be focused on in the EFL classroom should be set up clearly, aiming at satisfying students' needs and expectations through the development and implementation of learning materials. In this respect, Graves (1997) defines goals as the general or overall long-term purposes of a course and objectives as the specific form in which goals will be attained. They are just "particular ways of formulating or stating content and activities" (Nunan, 1988, p. 60). Setting goals and objectives gives a sense of direction and content framework for teachers in regard to course planning. It composes a map of the territory to be explored in which the destination is made up by the goals; and the objectives by the various points of the path to go along. It also helps teachers determine the appropriate content and activities for the course; as well as help students to become aware of what they are doing in the course. All in all, stating learning goals and objectives prior to developing materials not only gives a sense of direction of the lesson or course, but also benefits the agents involved in the teaching and learning endeavours to the degree that students

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undergo a successful non- threatening learning process and teachers improve their teaching practice.

Conceptualizing Content /Designing a Syllabus

This third component encompasses the incorporation of language aspects and language learning development procedures that are vital to the course progress. Even though the definition of a syllabus seems quite simple, its design demands accurate knowledge of the teaching and learning processes. Etymologically speaking, a syllabus means a "label" or "table"; and Altman and Cashin (1992 in Pardo and Tellez, 2009) pinpoint that a syllabus aims at communicating to students what the course intends to be, the reasons for teaching it, its destination, and the requirements to pass it. However, following Graves' description (1997), a syllabus can be considered a complex living entity under permanent change because there is never a perfect version of a syllabus, but rather one in which four focal points, namely, the language view, the learning and the learners' focus as well as the social context factor plays a central role.

The previous reasons lead us to affirm that we cannot refer to the evolution of course and materials content conceptualizations without considering the changes that, throughout history, have taken place in teaching methods and approaches, language acquisitions insights, and educational milieus. They have, to a great extent, permeated materials production starting with the structural view of language, then moving forward to a four-skill based language approach, later to a more communicative use of the target language, and finally to the development of cognitive, communicative and contextual competencies. All these adjustments have allowed for self-directed learning, cultural knowledge and awareness, and global communication.

Selecting and Developing Materials and Activities

Selecting materials and activities for our students is not a haphazard decision; it is one that embraces making effective and opportune decisions for their benefit. That is why we utterly agree with Graves (1997) who had the conception that any text by itself is not the course, but rather a tool that can be divided or cut up into components and then rearranged so as to suit the needs, abilities, interest, and expectations of the students comprising a course. Therefore, textbooks can be modified to incorporate activities that encourage students and move them beyond the constraints of the textbook.

In fact, a proper selection of activities must consider a range of factors such as usefulness in attaining the course purpose; suitability of students' age, interests, needs and expectations; availability of use; and plausibility of being adjusted up or down according to students' particular learning styles. Ideally, learners should be exposed to a

set of carefully planned, graded, sequenced and very well-articulated learning activities that will eventually enhance students' self-confidence and self-worth as a result of learning at their own pace and in their own styles. Moreover, an appropriate selection of activities will simultaneously allow teachers to make autonomous opportune decisions that foster a harmonious and efficient development of their classes and the attainment of students' learning objectives.

Organization of Content and Activities

In materials development, both content and activities could be structured in three distinct fashions known as the building, the recycling, and the sequence and matrix approaches. The first one gradually moves from the simplest to the most complex activities, from the general to the specific ones, and from the concrete to the abstract. The second one provides students with a learning challenge in terms of a new skill area, a different type of activity, or new focus. The third one follows a consistent sequence to be fulfilled within a given period. Although tables and webs are excellent tools to organize content, any graphic representation or illustration can be useful. Teachers' creativity can easily represent content and activities through a rainbow, a racing route, a landscape, etc.

Evaluation

Evaluation is a permanent component of the course development process that serves, among other purposes, to diagnose specific strengths and weakness, and assess students' achievement in a course programme (Pardo and Tellez, 2009). Brown (cited in Johnson, 1989 in Pardo and Tellez, 2009) identifies two types of evaluation: formative and summative. The former takes place during the implementation of the course and provides information about students' achievements and shortcomings and the extent to which needs are met, aiming at adjusting it while being developed. The latter, on the other hand, occurs at the end of a course and gives information about both students' overall achievement and the effectiveness of the course for future implementation.

Overall, teachers are to fulfill the dual process of stating goals and objectives, and asking students questions at both the beginning and the end of each unit, which will help them make decisions about skills and topics to be assessed, and identify what students know and what they need to refine. Thus, pre-and post-reflective questions about the materials allow teachers to detect flaws and so reexamine students' needs, re-organize syllabuses, and reselect activities aimed at meeting and challenging students' needs and learning.

Resources and Constraints

Teachers ought to be resourceful and then adapt to the tangible or intangible givens and lacks of their teaching situation in so far as it allows them to make down-to-earth sense of all the processes involved in developing materials. Graves (1997 in Patel, 2011) highlights how resourceful teachers can become in the absence of physical or technological resources, such as a classroom, books, technology, time, and even furniture. In other words, the lack of physical resources may encourage teachers to use available resources. Teacher-developed materials boost not only effective learning settings and outcomes, but also teachers' pedagogical practice performance. On the one hand, students' self-confidence and self-worth will be enhanced as a result of learning at their own pace, in their own styles, and in an enjoyable, non-threatening atmosphere that will keep their motivation up. On the other hand, opportune teachers' decision-making will foster a harmonious and efficient development of their classes and the accomplishment of students' learning objectives.

Effective materials make learners feel comfortable and confident because both the content and type of activities are perceived by them as significant and practical to their lives. However, the teaching materials by themselves are not sufficient to create effective teaching and learning settings since a lively EFL/ESL classroom depends largely on good materials used in creative and resourceful ways. Therefore, in the materials designed, language teachers need to lead their students to have materials interact appropriately with their needs and interests in order to facilitate learning.

Conclusion

The learner's needs are of utmost importance in materials adaptation; and so must be ascertained and factored into the process. The teacher must also be clear as to his goals and objectives for the task. He must have a clear picture in his mind of the content or syllabus to which material is being developed. This should be followed by the ability to select, organize, and develop materials and activities for lesson units. Adapted materials must be subjected to evaluation at various stages of production and usage to ensure effectiveness and realization of set objectives. The journey into adaptation began due to constraints and limitation/inadequacy of available resources. Therefore, adaptation would be considered successful at the end if this problem has been resolved. Materials often control the teaching, since teachers and learners tend to rely heavily on them. Materials that are appropriate for a particular class need to have an underlying instructional philosophy, approach, method and technique which suit the students and their needs. Teachers need to look for good materials, both commercial and non-commercial, all the time. When the teachers decide to adapt authentic or created

materials, it means that they are bridging the gap between the classroom and the world (Pardo and Tellez, 2009).

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